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RETROSPECTIVE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BANKING SYSTEM: THE PLACE OF SYSTEMICALLY IMPORTANT BANKS IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

Stages of development of the banking system of Ukraine during 1991-2021 are highlighted in the article, the peculiarities of functioning at the present stage, taking into account the factors that hinder the effective functioning of the domestic banking sector are analyzed. The economic meaning of the concept of "systemically important bank" is substantiated, and the place of systemically important banks in the banking system of Ukraine is determined. The priority directions of development of the domestic banking sector, increasing of its stability and competitiveness due to the development of systemically important banks in Ukraine in order to ensure economic growth are described. The impact of financial risks on the activities of the largest systemically important banks of Ukraine by building a mathematical and econometric model was determined.

Keywords: stages of development of the banking system, systemically important financial institutions, system-forming banks, financial risks.

Our present at the global level is characterized by tendencies to rapid growth of both economic and political instability. Rapid changes in operating conditions, active internal processes and the influence of external factors lead to constant economic transformations, to which the domestic banking system must adapt. Banks have a significant impact on production and the economic situation in the country, so to ensure the stability of economic processes it is necessary to intensify and guarantee the sustainable development of the banking, financial and economic system. Particular attention should be paid to managing the stability, stability and solvency of systemically important banks, as they are the focus of significant assets, liabilities and capital.

Therefore, the significance of the retrospective of the formation of the banking system of Ukraine and the determination of the role of systemically important banks in it, the presence of their functioning problems, the need to develop special measures for their regulation and supervision determine the importance of addressing these issues in domestic banking practice.

The following tasks are solved in the article: to discern the essence of the concept of "banking system"; consider the stages of development of the banking system of Ukraine; generalize scientific approaches to the interpretation of the essence of the concept of "systemically important bank"; determine the place of systemically important banks of Ukraine in the banking system; to analyze the impact of financial risks on the activities of the largest systemically important banks in Ukraine by building a mathematical and economic

model.

To solve the tasks set, general scientific and specific methods of scientific knowledge were used. Dialectical method - to determine the essence of systemically important banks. Logical-historical method - to study the stages of formation of the banking system of Ukraine. Methods of analysis, synthesis and comparative analysis - to determine the effectiveness of the development of the banking system and study the role of systemically important banks in it. Graphical method - for visual display of the results of the study. Methods of econometric model building - to analyze the impact of financial risks on the activities of the largest systemically important banks in Ukraine.

Now, the banking system of Ukraine is moving towards the modernization of service delivery technologies, which, in turn, increases the competitiveness of domestic financial institutions and promotes the integrating into world markets. However, for decades, the banking system of Ukraine has gone through a difficult path from formation to development and stabilization in the context of globalization processes.

Due to the concentration of financial resources and lending to priority sectors of the economy, the banking system plays a significant role in the process of the country's economic development. Therefore, ensuring the activities of systemically important financial institutions remains an important aspect in the process of transforming the domestic banking system under the financial imbalance, the slow creation of the necessary legislative framework and globalization shifts.

In 1991, Ukraine became an independent state, so the difficult path of forming a young country began from this period. Being part of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics left an imprint on all domestic systems, including the banking sector in need of immediate reform. Therefore, the first documented step towards building the banking system was the adoption of the Law "On Banks and Banking Activity" [1].

In general, the concept of the banking system is interpreted by scientists ambiguously, and the existing definitions of the banking system can be divided into two groups: the first can include those according to which the banking system is only a set of banks and banking institutions, and the second - the definition according to which the banking system also includes financial and credit institutions that do not have the status of a bank. Based on the above, we can distinguish a narrowed and expanded approach to the definition of the banking system. At the same time, in any case, the banking system is a two-level one: the Central Bank belongs to the first level, and all other institutions to the second [2].

Thus, according to the legislation, the banking system of Ukraine consists of the National Bank of Ukraine and other banks, as well as branches of foreign banks established and operating on the territory of Ukraine [1].

It is logical that scientists assert that "the banking system does not arise as a result of a mechanical combination of individual banks, but is based on a pre-developed concept, within which each type of bank and each individual bank occupies a certain place" [3]. All institutions of the banking system work and operate within the framework of one monetary mechanism.

The banking system has a wide range of features, but we included the next [2, 4]:

- Organization (characterized by the presence of rules of conduct for all entities that belong to it. All

banking institutions operating in Ukraine act in accordance with the requirements of the current legislation);

- A combination of elements (individual banks, with the exception of the National Bank of Ukraine (NBU), are elements of the banking system that operate for profit);

- Hierarchy (as noted above, the banking system of Ukraine is a two-level one, however, each individual entity belonging to the system can also belong to a wider system (global);

- Dynamism and adaptability (the banking system is constantly evolving and adapting to rapid changes in the economic sphere);

- Closeness (the banking system is a closed type system, characterized by the concentration of its subjects on established activities in the monetary sphere, where a significant share of banking information is controlled by national legislation and cannot be transferred to other systems);

- Communicativeness (in the banking system there is communication between its constituent entities and other entities).

The formation and development of the banking system of Ukraine are ambiguous, because it is characterized by the passage of significant reforms on the basis of the banks of the USSR to the development of innovations in the field of financial solutions (Fig.1).

We consider it appropriate to single out the following stages of the development of the banking system of Ukraine:

- stage of origin;
- stage of reform;
- stage of permanent growth and strengthening of globalization processes;
- crisis stage;
- stage of post-crisis recovery;
- stage of the banking crisis;
- stage of stabilization.

Figure 1. Stages of development of the banking system of Ukraine

Source: compiled by the authors.

At the stage of its origin, Ukrainian commercial banks were re-registered and the NBU was established on the basis of the Ukrainian Republican Bank State Bank of the USSR. The emergence of a significant number of banks caused the so-called "boom", during which 230 banking institutions were registered in Ukraine. In the foreign exchange market, the ruble

ceased to function: karbovanets was introduced into circulation.

The reform phase began with the aim of overcoming the negative consequences of the banking crisis under the influence of hyperinflation. By that time, the number of banks had significantly decreased, bank capital did not grow, and their financial condition only worsened. As a result of the "boom" in the market,

small banks functioned, which did not have a significant impact on the development of economic activity, but were problematic, and therefore reduced the level of confidence in banks. The introduction of the monetary reform, including the transition to international accounting standards to stabilize the banking system, contributed to the creation of conditions for overcoming inflationary processes. To minimize risks in the banking sector, the NBU introduced the creation of required reserves for all banks.

After 2001 a stage of permanent growth and strengthening of globalization processes began. The revision of the legislative framework and changes in the regulation of banking activities in accordance with the requirements of the Basel Committee took place. The economy was recovering, investment was growing, so the level of lending was growing [5].

For the first time since the Orange Revolution in 2004, international capital has entered the Ukrainian market. During this period, banks were actively expanding their network because foreigners were interested in banks with many branches, but, unfortunately, in 2008 the whole world was shaken by the financial crisis in the mortgage market for individuals [6].

The crisis phase affected every country, and especially affected the activities of the banking sector. The events of this period led to a decrease in the solvency and liquidity of some banks in Ukraine, so the nationalization of large domestic banks. It is worth noting that after the global crisis, in April 2009, the Financial Stability Board was established, and then together with the Basel Committee the concept of "systemically important bank" was introduced and new capital requirements for banks were created taking into account systemic importance [7]. Then a methodological basis was laid for studying the phenomenon of systemically important banks.

The Basel Committee defines systemically important banks as financial institutions whose failure or possible problems would result in significant losses to the entire financial system and to the economy as a whole due to their size, complexity and systemic interconnectedness [7].

The influence of systemically important banks on the country's banking sector is especially acute during periods of crisis and occurs when a bank has a liquidity deficit and the need to recognize the bank as insolvent, which has two alternative cases: allowing the liquidation or preventing the liquidation of the bank.

It should be noted that during the crisis of 2008-2009, the necessary conditions were organized in Ukraine to prevent the bankruptcy of Prominvestbank and Nadra Bank, which was of great importance for the development of Ukraine's economy. After all, the bankruptcy of systemically important banks leads to large-scale losses of taxpayers' funds by providing them with significant refinancing amounts and payments of guaranteed deposits, and the size of banks affects the amount of public funds needed to minimize the impact of bankruptcy.

Since the beginning of 2010, the post-crisis recovery of the banking system has begun. Bank credit risk management tools have been introduced, corporate governance in banks has been improved and e-banking services have been actively introduced in connection with globalization.

However, the most difficult stage for the banking system of Ukraine began in 2014, the consequences of which were observed until 2017. The occupation of the territories in the East of the country was a factor of the significant economic instability, including the devaluation of the hryvnia and inflation, which have led to a sharp decline in bank liquidity.

The banking crisis of this period led to changes in the structure of the banking system and led to the historically low public confidence in the banking sector. Within this period, there was a large bank purge, which resulted in the withdrawal of more than 100 banking institutions from the market (fig.2). It should be noted that the crisis phenomena of this period arose at a time when the consequences of the global crisis of 2008-2009 were not finally overcome and the system did not form a sufficient internal ability to withstand the negative influence of the external environment.

Figure 2. Number of banks in Ukraine for the period 2008-2021

Source: compiled by the authors according to [8].

Systemically important banks play a special role in the modern domestic banking system, the largest of which are PJSC Privatbank, PJSC Oschadbank, PJSC Ukreximbank, PJSC Ukrgasbank and PJSC Raiffeisen

Bank Aval. Confirmation of the systemic importance of these banks is the size of the share of assets in the banking sector (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Share of assets of the 5 largest systemically important banks

Source: compiled by the authors according to the NBU [9]

Bankruptcy of systemically important banks can provoke moral destructuring of the banking sector, as they are financed by the state even under adverse conditions through refinancing and recapitalization. Therefore, to maintain the liquidity and solvency of banks, including systemically important banks, the National

Bank of Ukraine provided significant amounts of refinancing loans to provide collateral during the crises of 2008-2009 and 2014-2015.

The banking sector is always accompanied by risks, therefore it is important to implement effective

risk management by each bank to ensure the development of their activities, in particular, this is the management of credit, currency, interest rate and liquidity risk.

Non-performing loans are a factor of the increasing credit risk, so many of them are a burden on the banking sector, especially for systemically important

banks. Since 2013, the share of problem loans has grown due to the low standards of solvency of the borrower. The high level of non-performing assets during the banking crisis is the result of the impact of crisis phenomena, as evidenced by the data in Figure (Fig. 4).

Figure 4.

Ratio of non-performing loans to the loan portfolio of the 5 largest systemically important banks in Ukraine

Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

The main reasons for the increase in the number of problem loans are next:

- the NBU assessment of the quality of the bank's assets, which prompted banks to recognize many loans as bad;
- introduction of a stricter definition of the term "non-performing loan (NPL)" in accordance with international practice (NBU Board Resolution 1351) [10];
- recognition by Privatbank of bad loans after nationalization.

One of the most resonant events, which became ambiguous, was the nationalization of Privatbank in 2016. This was the first case of nationalization of such a large bank, as it was determined that the entire financial and economic situation in the country depends on Privatbank. According to the NBU, the bank's problems were systemic and accumulated over the years, and

97% of the bank's loans were provided to companies related to its shareholders.

In the process of formation, the banking system of Ukraine was significantly affected by currency risk, as it was the cause of slow economic growth due to devaluation and bank bankruptcy. The NBU has set the value of open currency position limits in order to avoid excessive exchange rate fluctuations and increase the liquidity of the banking market.

The limits on long and short currency positions of banks were doubled in 2020, from 5% to 10%. In order to avoid possible losses in the event of a change in the exchange rate, the regulator limits the size of the bank's positions to 10% of the volume of regulatory capital. The dynamics of these ratios for the largest systemically important banks was analyzed in Figures 5 and 6, which reflect the indicators of the limits of a long and short open currency position, respectively.

Figure 5. Dynamics of compliance with L13-1 by the largest systemically important banks
Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

As we can see, among the surveyed banks, Privatbank and Oschadbank significantly violated the long open currency position, especially before the Covid-19 pandemic, when their assets exceeded the amount of off-balance sheet liabilities in foreign currencies more than 20 times. This situation outlines the significant currency risk for banks in the event of an appreciation of the hryvnia (national currency) against foreign currencies. However, starting from the second half of 2020, these banks significantly minimized the gap between assets and liabilities, which at the end of the study was 135% for Oschadbank and 80% for Privatbank. There was a significant difference in the dynamics of the limit for Oschadbank in February 2021, when the bank sharply maximized liabilities in foreign currency and opened a short currency position (see Figure

6), but then again sharply increased assets and ratio L13-1 to 125%.

The presence of an open short currency position indicates that the bank's liabilities in foreign currency exceed its assets, which means that the bank will face currency risk in the event of an increase in the exchange rate of foreign currencies relative to the national one. During the study period, all banks observed this limit, except Oschadbank. This bank has been increasing the gap between liabilities and assets since October 2019 and reached its peak in February 2020, after which it began to decline again. By the end of the study, all banks complied with the L13-2 ratio and did not expose themselves to significant currency risk of an increase in the foreign exchange rate, which is more typical for the realities of the Ukrainian banking system.

Figure 6. Dynamics of L13-2 compliance by the largest systemically important banks
Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

The NBU has changed its approach to regulating banks' liquidity by amending legislation in line with Basel III requirements. [11] Standards have been introduced to ensure the financial stability of banks, such as LCR (liquidity coverage ratio) and NSFR (net stable funding ratio). At the beginning of 2020, a systemic importance buffer was also introduced for systemic banks [12, 13, 14].

In general, the introduction of the new banking regulation instruments was scheduled for 2020, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, they were postponed: the

systemic risk buffer (SRB), the capital conservation buffer (CCB) and the net stable funding ratio (NSFR). Therefore, as a result, Ukraine faced a crisis due to the COVID-19 pandemic without buffers, as they were not created in advance.

A liquidity ratio that has already begun to be used in practice is the Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR). The dynamics of implementation of the NSFR standard by systemically important Ukrainian banks can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Dynamics of NSFR compliance by the largest systemically important banks

Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

This standard was created to encourage banks to long-term sources of funding. According to the plan for the development of the banking sector, domestic banks, including systemically important banks, in 2022 should reach 100% of the NSFR. However, now all banks from among the selected systemically important ones fully comply with the standard.

The liquidity coverage ratio entered is divided into LCRac (for all currencies) and LCRfc (in foreign currency). The standard LCR values have changed from 80% in 2019 to 100% in 2021. The dynamics of the implementation of the 5 largest systemically important banks of the LCRvv standard can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Dynamics of LCRac compliance in the largest systemically important banks

Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

It is necessary to consider the dynamics of fulfillment by the 5 largest systemically important banks of the LCR standard (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Dynamics of LCRfc compliance by the largest systemically important banks

Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

Next in our analysis will be a description of interest rate risk specific to systemically important banks. This type of risk is realized in the event of unfavorable changes in interest rates and includes risks: changes in the cost of resources (arising due to differences in maturity), changes in the shape or slope of the yield curve, basic (implemented due to a weak relationship between

rates at different instruments) and the right to choose (in case of refusal) [15].

It is important to consider the gaps between interest rates on the main banking operations - credit and deposit. In practice, the larger the gap between these rates, the more the bank is protected from interest rate risk due to higher margins. The dynamics of the gaps between the rates is represented in Figure 10.

Figure 10.

Dynamics of the gap between the loan and deposit interest rates of the largest systemically important banks

Source: compiled by the authors according to [9].

Figure 10 clearly shows the trend towards an increase in the gap between interest rates on lending and deposit operations after the banking crisis of 2014-2016, when the banking system of Ukraine became more transparent and cleared of unscrupulous banks.

Thus, by reducing the number of institutions in the market and weeding out captive and other troubled banks, banking institutions were able to afford to hedge more against interest rate risk by maximizing the gap between lending and liability rates. As can be seen from

Figure 9, the top three by the size of the gap are: Privatbank (the largest in terms of assets and accumulated profit), Raiffeisen Bank Aval (having a reputation as one of the most stable in the Ukrainian market) and Oshchadbank (focused on consumer services). Therefore, as of the end of 2021, the studied banks had a gap of 5 to 10 p.p., which indicates that the realization of interest rate risk for them is potentially weak.

Thus, from the above analysis, we can see that banking activity is accompanied by a significant group of risks that affect the development of the banking and

Table 1. Correlation matrix for JSC "Oshchadbank"

Years	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4
2017	3,11	0,0457	0,7672	-0,1109	0,0457
2018	2,54	0,1110	0,7198	-0,0638	0,1424
2019	2,75	0,0360	0,9765	0,9400	0,0320
2020	2,53	0,0313	0,8510	0,9350	0,0370
2021	2,72	0,0448	0,4887	0,9246	0,0448

Source: calculated by the authors.

To solve the problem of multicollinearity between variables using a correlation matrix, it was found that X1 and X2 are most correlated with the rest of the indicators, so they were removed.

The next step is regression analysis according to the bank data. The results obtained made it possible to compose the regression equation (1).

$$Y=3,2374-0,0332X3-5,6309X4 \quad (1)$$

We can conclude that with an increase in X3 (interest rate risk) by 1 point, the financial stability of Oshchadbank will decrease by 0.0332 points, and with an increase in X4 (currency risk) - the financial stability of the bank will decrease by 5.6309 points.

The coefficient of determination was 0.79, that is, it approaches 1, which means that the model is adequate and suitable for its use in economic analysis.

When checking the coefficients of the equation for significance, it was found that the average value of the approximation error is 3.52% and is within acceptable limits.

Thus, we found the dependence of the stability of Oshchadbank JSC on such financial risks as interest rate and currency. Although, in order to avoid multicollinearity, parameters such as liquidity risk and credit risk were not taken into account, the low value of the approximation indicates the quality of the constructed model.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The banking system of Ukraine has gone through a number of stages of development (the stage of inception, the stage of reform, the stage of permanent growth and strengthening of globalization processes, the crisis stage, the stage of post-crisis recovery, the stage of the banking crisis, the stage of stabilization), during which it experienced both significant achievements and declines as a result of global crisis phenomena. In Ukraine, a significant role is assigned to systemically important banks, the number of which has significantly decreased in recent years, due to changes in approaches to the classification of banks. Systemically important banks have a number of specific features that form their systemic importance, namely, a niche part of

economic system. It is necessary to construct an economic-mathematical model for assessing the impact of financial risks on the financial stability of a bank based on the financial stability index of systemically important banks. The data for the construction were used from the performance indicators of one of the largest state-owned systemically important banks - Oshchadbank. The data for building the model are given in Table 1, where Y is the scoring index of the bank's stability, X1 - liquidity risk, X2 - credit risk, X3 - interest rate risk, X4 - currency risk.

operations in the market, significant volumes of inter-bank transactions, and the availability of specific services. Banking activity is accompanied by a significant group of risks that affect the development of the banking and economic system, therefore, for the development of the infrastructure of the country's financial and credit market, it is important to ensure the activities of precisely those banks that are the system-forming elements of the market.

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